

Contribution of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee in Higher Education

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Abstract

This research paper discusses the background of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, its role in the field of higher education and the special efforts made to make the students fit for the times.

Keywords

Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Scholarship, Educational Institutions, Placement.

Introduction

Bhai Gurdas Ji has said that 'As seven temples are built with gold, teach one word to a disciple.' According to Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, "Education is the most powerful weapon, which you can use to change the world". Education is the companion of the human race. Man learns something every day. Therefore, education is a continuous and lifelong process. It starts when a child is born and continues till the last moment of death. In a broad sense, education is life & life is education. Education is that source of light which shows our path in different spheres of life. Education makes us civilized human beings. Education is very important for the progress of an individual and society. That is why education is called the third eye of a human being. Thus, education develops the student in all aspects. Knowledge is considered the best friend of a human being. It is written in the Holy Quran, "It is better to give education to one's child than to give gold in charity".

The concept of education is very important in Shri Guru Granth Sahib Ji. Apart from the six Gurus, the Bani of 15 Bhagats, 11 Bhats & 3 Gursikhs recited in 31 ragas, although the thoughts related to education are not directly given, still, by studying Gurbani in depth, we find many verses in which light has been shed on various aspects of education. In the Dakshina Onkar Bani and in three special Bani, in which the alphabet has been interpreted poetically, a serious discussion related to education has been made. These Bani discuss under the headings: - *'Mahla 1 Patti Likhi' – the importance of education, *'Mahla 3 Patti' – the purpose of education, *'Bavan Akhri Kabir Jiu Ki' – education – the characteristics of the giver, the Satguru and the scholar.

Objective of study

1. The study aims to analyze the historical development and spread of higher Educational Institutions established and managed by SGPC.
2. The research purposes to examine the contribution of Shiromani Gurdwara Prabandhak Committee in promoting value based education integrated with Sikh Ethics.
3. To evaluate the role of SGPC in improving access to higher education in Rural, Urban and Disadvantaged Communities.

Review of Literature

1. Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee Shri Amritsar, 100th Anniversary of Establishment of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee Shri Amritsar History, Works and Achievements, Amritsar, 2020 highlights the role of SGPC in promoting education and managing Sikh Institutions. It explains how SGPC established and supported Colleges and Universities to provide quality higher education. The book also emphasizes SGPC's efforts to combine academic learning with Sikh values and ethics. Overall, it shows SGPC's significant contribution to developing higher education in the Sikh Community.
2. The official SGPC website (www.sgpc.net) provides detailed information about its extensive educational initiatives, including SGGs World University, SGRD Medical and Dental Colleges, and numerous schools. It highlights the SGPC's commitment to promoting Sikh values through education and its efforts to expand access to quality higher education. The site also outlines recent programs like the Nishchay Academy, which prepares Sikh students for competitive exams such as UPSC and PPSC
3. Roop Singh, Panth Sewak (President of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee), Amritsar, 2015 highlights the organizational role and leadership functions of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee. It provides insights into the SGPC's service-oriented approach towards the Sikh community and its institutions. The work also throws light on SGPC's contribution in the field of education, including the establishment and management of schools and colleges, thereby shaping higher education in Punjab.

Main Text

Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee and Education

As soon as the British occupied Punjab, they started establishing Christian missionary stations or missions in central places. In 1851 AD, there were only about one and a half Christians in Punjab, but in 1880 AD, their number increased to more than one and a half thousand. Apart from the direct Christian missionary centers, the Christians also opened mission schools in various places to further their missionary work. In them and in government schools, the Christian religious book 'Anjeel' was taught to every student and the children were motivated to embrace Christianity by giving education, sermons and enticements.

As a result, many Sikh students started abandoning their religion and adopting Christianity. In 1873 AD, 4 Sikh students of the Mission School Amritsar - Atar Singh, Sadhu Singh, Santokh Singh and Aya Singh etc., were ready to become Christians. On learning this, many Sikh chiefs tried very hard to prevent these students from adopting Christianity by explaining it to them. This incident inspired the intelligent Sikhs that it was necessary to take measures to protect the Panth from such destruction and attacks. Ultimately, this incident became the immediate reason for the start of the Singh Sabha movement. Its main objective was the spread of education, under which Khalsa schools and colleges were opened at different places to impart religious education to Sikh students. In 1877 AD, Bhai Gurmukh Singh introduced the Punjabi language in the Oriental College of the Punjab University, and he himself was appointed as a teacher of Punjabi. In 1883 AD, the 'Khalsa Press' was also launched for easy and good printing. In the last decade of the 19th century, a large number of Singh Sabhas and Khalsa Diwans were established at different places. Its main objective was to eradicate illiteracy and to run the Sikh educational movement rapidly. An important achievement of the Chief Khalsa Diwan in the field of education is the establishment of the Sikh Educational Conference in 1908 AD. The nature of this educational institution is non-governmental, and this institution works under the patronage of the Chief Khalsa Diwan Amritsar. At the beginning of this conference, the number of Khalsa schools was only 8, which by 1947 AD, with enthusiastic and continuous efforts, reached 340.

During the Sikh struggle, the management of the Gurdwara Sahibs came into the hands of the Mahants. The Mahants of many Gurdwaras became so corrupt that it became difficult for the Sikh community to tolerate the evils being done by them. In such circumstances, to run the management of the Gurdwara Sahibs according to the Gurdwara etiquette, the great personalities of that time came together and on 15 November, 1920 AD, established the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, also known as the "PARLIAMENT OF SIKH NATION"; which was registered on 30 April, 1921 AD.

Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee was formed mainly for the maintenance of Gurdwaras, management of religious Panthic works and propagation of Sikhism. The main objective of this organization is to propagate Sikhism as well as to provide quality education to the Sikh community. The education sector of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee is not limited to academic knowledge only, but also moral, modern and religious aspects of the youth. S. G. P. C. is running hundreds of schools, colleges and universities in states like Punjab, Chandigarh, Himachal, Haryana and Rajasthan. Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee has promoted the education of girls by opening many girls' schools and colleges. This organization has also included modern methods such as computer education, scientific labs, libraries, technical courses, foreign language education, as well as providing online learning materials in its institutions, so that students can become employable. Scholarships, stipends and other facilities are provided as financial assistance to the students of poor and backward classes so that they can also become a part of the times by getting an education.

Under this, many educational institutions, including universities, degree colleges, medical colleges, dental colleges, engineering colleges, senior secondary schools, public schools and sports academies etc., are running successfully. More than 1500 professors and other staff members are serving in these universities, big institutes, colleges and schools and more than 64000 students were receiving education during the year 2019-20. In the present times, for the transparent management of quality education, the Directorate of Education was established in 2007, which is functioning as a sub-office at Panth Ratan Jathedar Tohra Institute of Advanced Studies in Sikhism, Bahadurgarh (Patiala).

Higher Education Institutions of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee

Shri Guru Granth Sahib World University was established in 2008 AD at Sri Fatehgarh Sahib by Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee to provide higher education to the students. Along with this, keeping in mind the health facilities, Medical College - Sri Guru Ramdas Institute of Medical Sciences and Research University, Walla, Sri Amritsar Sahib and Miri Piri Institute of Medical Science and Research, Shahbad Markanda, Haryana, Dental College - Sri Guru Ramdas Dental Institute, Mal Mandi, Sri Amritsar Sahib, Nursing College - Sri Guru Ramdas Nursing College, Walla, Sri Amritsar Sahib, are running very sincerely. Apart from this, to keep the students up to date in the field of professional education, the Engineering College - Guru Nanak Eng. College, Ludhiana and Baba Banda Singh, Bahadur Eng. College, Sri Fatehgarh Sahib, Polytechnic College - Guru Nanak Eng. Polytechnic College, Ludhiana and Baba Banda Singh Bahadur Eng. Polytechnic College, Sri Fatehgarh Sahib, has been established.

To further promote higher education, degree colleges have been established by the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, such as B.Ed. Colleges - Mata Sahib Kaur Khalsa Girls College of Education, Dhama Majra (Patiala), Nankana Sahib College of Education Kot Gangurai (Ludhiana), Aided/Unaided Colleges - General Shivdev Singh Diwan Gurbachan Singh Khalsa College, Patiala, Guru Nanak College, Budhlada, Mansa, Sri Guru Tegh Bahadur Khalsa College, Sri Anandpur Sahib, Guru Nanak College, Batala, District Gurdaspur, Babbar Akali Memorial Khalsa College, Garhshankar, District Hoshiarpur, Khalsa College, Garhdiwala, District Hoshiarpur, Sant Baba Dalip Singh Memorial Khalsa College, Dumeli, District Kapurthala, Guru Nanak Khalsa College, Droli Kalan, District Jalandhar, Mata Gujri College, Fatehgarh Sahib, Guru Nanak College for Girls, Shri Muktsar Sahib, Guru Nanak College, Moga, Guru Nanak Khalsa College of Arts and Science and Commerce, Matunga, Mumbai, Guru Nanak Institute of Management Studies, Matunga, Mumbai, Guru Nanak Institute of Research and Development, Matunga, Mumbai, Baba Ajay Singh Khalsa College, Gurdas Nangal, Gurdaspur.

Un-aided Colleges

Tari-Shatabdi Guru Gobind Singh Khalsa College, Sri Amritsar, Shaheed Baba Jiwan Singh Khalsa College, Satlani Sahib, Sri Amritsar, Guru Arjan Dev Khalsa College, Chohla Sahib, Tarn-Taran, Mata Sahib Kaur Girls College, Talwandi Sabo, Bathinda, Mata Sahib Kaur Girls College, Talwandi Bhai, Ferozepur, Mata Damodari Kanya Collegiate Senior Secondary School, Droli Bhai, Moga, Miri Piri Khalsa College, Bhadaur, Barnala, Mata Sahib Kaur Girls College, Gehal, Barnala, Shri Guru Teg Bahadur Khalsa College for Girls, Pind Akar, Patiala, Guru Hargobind Sahib Khalsa Girls College, Karhali Sahib, Patiala, Mata Ganga Khalsa College for Girls, Kotan, Ludhiana, Guru Gobind Singh Khalsa College for Women, Jhar Sahib, Ludhiana, Mata Sundari Khalsa College Girls, Nising-Karnal, Haryana, Shri Guru Harkrishan Sahib Khalsa College, Panjokhra Sahib, Ambala, Bhai Behlon Khalsa Girls College, Fafre Bhai Ke, Mansa, Mata Gujri Khalsa College, Kartarpur, Jalandhar, Shri Guru Gobind Singh Khalsa College, Bhagta Bhai Ka, Bathinda, Dashmesh Khalsa College, Zirakpur, Mohali, Bibi Sharan Kaur Khalsa College, Chamkaur Sahib, Ropar, Bhai Sangat Singh Khalsa College, Banga, Shaheed Bhagat Singh Nagar, Shaheed Bhai Mani Singh Khalsa College, Longowal, Sangrur, etc.

Other Initiatives

1 Nishchay Prasashki Academy

The Directorate of Education of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Bahadurgarh, Patiala has initiated Nishchay Prasashki Academy at Gurdwara Kalgidhar Niwas, Chandigarh to provide free education to 50 Sikh children for the preparation of PCS, IAS and UPSC examinations.

2 Free Education for Gursikh Girls

Due to the efforts of SGPC, 250 Gursikh girls are provided free education at Mata Sahib Kaur Girls College, Talwandi Sabo and 100 Gursikh girls at Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University, Sri Fatehgarh Sahib, under the Mata Nanaki Ji Academic and Religious Free Education Scheme, where the hostel, food, and drinking water for the girls are also managed by the Dharam Prachar Committee, Sri Amritsar Sahib.

3 Religious Examinations and Scholarships

The Dharam Prachar Committee of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee organizes religious examinations every year under the prescribed syllabus to provide information about the Sikh religion, history, the Sikh code of conduct and Gurbani to the students. The students who come first, second and third are given a scholarship of Rs. 4100, Rs. 3100 and Rs. 2100 respectively, and Amritdhari students pursuing a graduation degree are given a scholarship of Rs. 8000/- and Amritdhari students pursuing a post-graduation degree are given a scholarship of Rs. 10,000/- annually.

4 Educational Budget

SGPC allocates a sum of Rs. 10,000/- from its budget every year. Some amount is reserved for the promotion of education. Rs. 1 crore 70 lakhs have been reserved for the education of Gursikh students from the annual budget of the year 2023-24.

5 Smart Classrooms

To keep the students up to date and to make them aware of IT, smart rooms have been set up in various colleges by the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee.

6 Placement

A central placement cell has been set up for all the colleges of SGPC, under which a week-long "Employment and Life Skills Training Program" is conducted for girls by Mahindra & Mahindra Company in collaboration with the Directorate of Education of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Bahadurgarh, Patiala. In these workshops, students are given free training to pass interviews and written papers. Many students are appointed in various companies through the services of the placement cell.

7 All-round development

The Dharam Prachar Committee of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee is running various propaganda campaigns from time to time, keeping in mind the all-round development of the students, like Gianu Parchandu Prashontri Competition, 'Shaan e Sikhi' (live on TV show), 'Gavahu Sachi Bani', etc., competitions are organized.

8 Agreement with foreign universities

The Directorate of Education, Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, has signed an agreement with the Guru Nanak Institute of Global Studies Canada, due to which there is no difficulty for the students to go abroad and study.

Conclusion

Thus, the leading organization of the Sikh Panth, Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, Shri Amritsar, came into existence after a long struggle and great sacrifices. Since its inception, this organization has not only made valuable contributions in the fields of religious, social, political and health, but has also left an indelible mark in the field of education. The admission and tuition fees of schools and colleges running under the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee have been kept low compared to other schools and colleges. Special discounts are also given to Gursikh students.

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